

Article

Analysis of Structure of Demand Response (DR) Communication in Smart Grid

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Abstract-

The hierarchical structure of the ISO/IEC 7498.1 model specification for demand response terminal architecture makes it possible to realize reliable communication between various systems/networks by clearly distinguishing services, interfaces, and protocols. Using the ISO hierarchical model as a guide, the SGAM approach to implementing a demand response system divides the logical communication process into five layers, each responsible for ensuring the authentication and security of a different DR terminal's inter-operability. Conventional electric meters must be swapped out for state-of-the-art, wireless, data-processing-capable devices in every building to implement demand management. Demand management is a multi-step process, the first of which is the installation of a smart meter. The meter may eventually be connected to smart home and commercial devices. Both the utility and the customer can use the smart meter to regulate when and how much power is consumed. For this reason, the advanced metering infrastructure (AMI) must prioritize trustworthy authentication and data protection.

Key words - Demand response, smart meter, RO PUF, Multigene Genetic Programming (MGGP), Authentication

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1. Introduction

Smart Grid (SG) is a new reformation from a regular electrical grid to an intelligent, thoughtful, and electronically managed system. Its vision is to modernize, monitor, protect, and optimize; optimization of its interconnected elements refers to the modernization of its protection system. It is an automated control system. Distribution system with high voltage and industrial consumer and automation systems, power storage installations and industrial and constructing automation systems, storage installations and end-use parties and their thermostats, appliance, electric cars, and different Home appliances "will operate intelligent, robust, innovative and optimized operation for electricity management [1]. The Smart grid is an alternative to the typical electrical energy gadget, a superior grid. Is it a complicated system including consumer empowerment and friendly and automatic response for contingency?

The SG is a complicated technology Because It includes desired characteristics of users' empowerment [2]. During contingency, it is user-friendly and automated. Another helpful feature of the SG is the bidirectional electrical and communication flow. Utilizing an effective Demand Response Program (DRP) with the prosumer's operation in SG will promote the availability of the power grid. The consumers, management, and infrastructure can adjust the length of business deals by their own choice in SG [3].

Authentications, privacy, and Security [4] are three of the biggest problems the smart grid faces in the future. The conventional network and the SG network are both different from each other. Here information network deals with highly confidential information. There is a lack of bidirectional [5] authentication between communicational entities, the risk of cyber-attacks, unauthorized access to the grid's energy, and revealing sensitive information about devices and grids to communicational entities. Here information confidentiality is the first promotion, then integrity [6], and the least data availability.

On the other hand, the SG network is responsible for the availability of information and protection of the information and then the data Authenticity and security [3]. With this background, we do the thesis to investigate the

influences of authentications of Demand response applications with residential users in Smart Grid. Then analyze the possible method to mitigate the effects of authentications and how to implement this into the SG- System.

2. Methodology and Model

A. Smart Grid Methodology

Smart grid methodology separates the concept of "user requirements" from the idea of "technical specifications": user requirements are defined as "what" is needed without involving any specific professional design or technology. In contrast, technical specifications are defined as "how" to implement this system and application to meet user requirements. IEC 62559 smart grid methodology applies to the design of power system communication and information solutions, including real-time simulation and emergency analysis, distributed generation and alternative energy, large-scale self-healing protection [10] and island protection, asset management and online equipment monitoring, demand response and real-time electricity price, power market participation and interaction, etc. Smart grid methodology is a part of system engineering science, which studies smart grids based on user demand.

In the process of studying the power demand response system, we should take into account the relevant collective needs of its managers, technical experts, industry standards, other power grid systems, equipment manufacturers, power users, etc., and study the connotation and top-level technical framework of the power demand response system which is applied to intelligent building scenarios efficiently, safely and interactively based on the needs. IEC 62559 provides a top-down system engineering method, which helps to map the requirements of the smart grid with the specific technology selection of information and communication technology, and corresponds the planning vision with the particular implementation scheme, to find the requirements target and standardization object for the standard formulation, that is, to solve the common requirements and specifications. As part of the smart grid system approach to some high-level concepts and principles of smart grid:

System integration, especially between the power system and its control and communication system. Open system based on standards and interoperable. User definition of applications and requirements. Technical solutions that can be mapped to requirements. Develop strategies for tiered solutions to minimize the adverse impact of future technology changes.

B. DR System Conceptual Model

DR system is divided into four domains, each of which has its own role to transmit information on different communication infrastructures. They realize the information exchange function among the systems of demand response through the demand response information (DRI) exchange interface. The conceptual model of DR system is shown in Figure 1. Related entities that have information interaction with demand response business, such as distribution operation management, market management, building management [11] and advanced measurement infrastructure (AMI), communicate with DR server through internal information exchange bus or application program interface of energy management system defined by IEC 61970. The system within the grid company will not communicate with each other through DRI, which is the information interface between the grid company and the users.

In the user domain, the power load of intelligent building is connected with DR terminal through Building Energy Management System (BEMS). As required, intelligent buildings can be directly connected to the power grid company's DR server or the third-party service provider's DR aggregation system. When the power grid is in emergency or there is an emergency predicted, DR dispatching management will define demand response events through DR server. When the event notification time arrives, the demand response automatic server will automatically send the demand response information to inform the user that a demand response event is about to occur. When the event start time arrives, the DR server automatically sends the demand response signal (including electricity price, reliability information, etc.) to the DR terminal installed in the user end. The DR terminal converts the demand response signal into various load reduction commands, such as adjusting lighting, adjusting air conditioning parameters, adjusting energy storage, etc.

Figure 1: Smart Grid Conceptual Model

3. Concept of Layer

A. DR Functional Layer

The functional layer is function-ate Information and communication technology (ICT) function. These functional layer must support the existing demand response business models, such as IL, CPP, DLC, etc., support the whole process of DR implementation, create plans, rate structures, signals, assessments, controls, settlements, etc. DR terminal must support DR Service requirements at different levels. According to DR Service classification, DR Service classification, service classification, DR interaction level can be classified into four levels, as shown DR interaction level develops from direct control level at the bottom to service-based interaction at the top.

The bottom layer is called "control", the second layer is called "device class service request" and the top two layers together are called "service request". This kind of service request interaction has decoupled service request and optional response; the role of DR terminal and server can change between interactions. Services typically transmit higher level requests that need to be completed, rather than detailed instructions on how to complete the required results. When the control interaction is most similar to the control of a specific device (for example, building automation), it requires device level information (function, control protocol). However, if you simply power off a simple device, you do not need to understand the device itself. In some control categories, the use cases are DLC cut off the power supply, and some energy management control signals that look more like the equipment level.

The high level of demand response interaction pays more attention to the user's independent choice, the corresponding user's responsibility will increase, the financial benefits and risks of participating in the DR plan will also be transferred to the user, and the uncertainty of the result of demand response events will also increase. Users improve or replace the existing devices and systems to communicate with the smart grid for the automation of load equipment. The stable DR interface can be used as a decoupling mechanism, so that the two domains of the electric domain and the user domain do not need to be closely tied together for interoperability. According to the interaction level of DR terminal, we can conclude six functions needed by demand response service: data communication function, information management function, transaction management function, automatic response function, effect evaluation function and security management function. The object types defined in the information layer are a series of data types and patterns, including physical data types (such as load power) and logical data types (such as user

identity definition). These data types are modeled by XML protocol or transmitted using XML as data carrier, forming XSD documents embedded in their XSD schema files.

Figure 2: Demand Response Functional layer

Data transmission or information exchange among power grid companies, third-party service providers and users mainly includes market interaction, transmission price and product definition information, transmission supporting services and operators' signals, transmission demand response requests and notifications, transmission of the indication of impending power failure, natural disasters or other special events, transmission direct interaction requests, transmission history or real-time capabilities Source usage (meter measurement), transmission of monitoring information. In addition, there are demand response events and supporting services and information for supporting services and market interaction needs.

This may include: registration, registration, communication effectiveness of resources, optional join or exit response to demand response event signals, status of load response, and appropriate baseline data. Interface information exchange includes information exchange among user equipment, systems, users and third-party service operators, and information exchange between users and power grid companies. Information exchange methods mainly include client / server, browser / server, publisher / subscriber. This layer provides the data content of interface information exchange required by demand response function, which may include response signal, price signal, load parameters (such as demand, forecast demand, storage availability), market transaction, energy use (electricity meter data), emergency signal broadcast by system operator and other energy related parameters, such as power quality.

B. Communication layer

The communication layer defines the way of information exchange between devices / systems using data objects and supporting ICT functions. The interface shall have a unified communication protocol and interface standard to respond to the event information released or forwarded by the upper layer and feedback the data information of the upper layer terminal participating in DR Support syntax interoperability and network interoperability to ensure connectivity between different networks. On the basis of communication layer, we can understand the semantics of different standards and protocols, and support a variety of business information.

The support of communication protocol is based on the service abstraction of information exchange interface, which consists of three key parts: service description, service operation and communication primitive. In the process of service invocation, we should first make clear the functions to be completed by the service, the operations needed to invoke the service, and the communication primitives needed to realize the calling function. In the process of service analysis, the requester and respond involved in the service should be found and determined from the perspective of users. Specifically, it should include the following contents: Service caller, service calling method, return data of calling service, input data of service, association between this service and other services.

In order to ensure the universality of the interface, the mapping method between services and various protocols is defined. The abstract services are mapped to specific communication networks and protocols such as HTTP, UDP / IP, TCP / IP, Ethernet, wifi, Zig-Bee, PLC, etc. the application of the system and equipment is isolated from the specific communication mode. Describes how to generate and exchange specific communication messages, which implement the defined information model and information exchange model. Referring to SGAM's description of demand response use cases, the network types required for information exchange mainly include user access network, distribution network, advanced measurement system return network, internal control center / internal data center network, backbone network and operation return network, which connect the equipment / system involved in DR business.

C. *Foundation user device layer*

This layer defines the underlying protocol stacks that may need to be mapped for demand response, such as Ethernet, wi-fi, zig-bee, PLC, rs.485, etc. This layer includes physical networking media, and takes the entire OSI environment as the basic communication facilities. The communication requirements include message, frequency, timing requirements, multicast, broadcast, uni-cast and so on. When the grid domain / user domain using different communication protocols sends data, DRI receives data, extracts useful information, parses the required services and rewrites them in a unified XML language, Finally, it is sent out. On the contrary, when the DRI receives the XML data, it can parse the application information and repackage it into the data form corresponding to the grid domain / user domain.

4. *Result and Discussion*

A. *Authentication of Smart Grid Network*

Authentication is the procedure of proving an identification to a given system, together with users and applications units [12]. In a typical Smart Grid network, there are hundreds of thousands of appliances interacting among-est each other. So concerned information exchange entities need to be bi-directional authenticated (13).

Types of Authentication in the Smart Grid (SG) Network can be categorized as follows:

- Appliance to Appliance
- Appliance to network
- User to Appliance / network

B. *Appliance to Appliance Authentication*

In the Smart home / building environment, a variety of smart appliance interface each other via home / building area network. Secure interface among appliance is a crucial for Smart Grid security. The authentication server (AS) of the SG device should authenticate all the related measurement. Apart from this, be secured from a variety of assaults such as impersonation, information forgery attack, etc. Several authentication and public key infrastructure mechanisms are proposed by Lee et al. [14] to provide mutual authentication between smart appliances. However, the safety evaluation of the scheme is now not discussed.

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C. *Network Authentication Value*

A mutual authentication between all the appliance and the Home Area Network is required. During an authentication, the cryptographic key of every system should be covered in opposition to any misuse theft, or attack over the network. Current techniques of defending cryptographic keys require consumer interaction, which is once more a downside or a loophole in the Smart Grid protection machine if the bi-directional authentication is no longer furnished between the person and the system. Pavard and Martin [15] designed a system, which presents hardware protection to the cryptographic key of precise system the usage of dynamic root of believe for dimension (DRTM) late launch functionality. A mutual authentication between all the appliance and the Home Area Network is required. During an authentication, the cryptographic key of every system should be covered in opposition to any misuse theft,

Figure. 3. Implementation model

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Table.1- layer value Result

Authentication Level	Ri (Response bits)	PBi (parity bits)	Ci (Challenge bits)	Time (ms)			
				PBi Generation Time	PBi Transfer Time	Ci Transfer Time	Total Authentication
L1 (L1)	128	64	1024	64	0.047	0.752	64.799
L2 (L2)	256	128	2048	128	0.094	1.504	129.598
L3 (L3)	512	256	4096	256	0.188	3.008	259.196
L4 (L4)	1024	512	8192	512	0.376	6.016	518.392
L5 (L5)	2048	1024	16384	1024	0.753	12.048	1036.801

D. User to Appliance / network

End Users play a vital function when in the beginning placing up the application and the network. It is essential as the malicious device and solid connections and divulge the non-public data of users. This can be finished by way of setting up an end user password to every machine and the community so that customers have manage over these entities. Vaidya et al. [16] proposed an authentication scheme for a cell Radio Frequency

The Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI) is bi-irectional network consisting bi-irectional network consisting software of the smart grid. The AMI enables two-way exchange between the smart meters and demand

response aggregator and utility center with the aid of associating system and information management software. The customers, retail suppliers, and utility corporations exchange, accumulate and distribute data through the AMI system. On the other hand, the utility corporations can obtain imperative load savings via the utilization of AMI system. The AMI infrastructure is a necessary part of the smart grid as it supports the information exchange to each customer's home area network to the utility center. The smart meters consistently communicate with the utility via AMI to perform in accordance to the scheduled demand response of the clients. Data exchanged between smart meters to utility, smart meter analyzing and renovation information to real-time pricing and demand response information of customers. To function these task, the device connected to the AMI system use multi-hop and hierarchical communication networks. The utility center, aggregator, smart meters and Home appliances are the principal aspects connected in the Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI) network.

Table.2. Advanced Metering Infrastructure

Authentication Level	Year(s)	Data Size (Megabyte)
Lable 1 (L1)	1	4.545
	5	22.725
	10	45.45
Lable 2 (L2)	1	2.273
	5	11.365
	10	22.73
Lable 3 (L3)	1	1.136
	5	5.68
	10	11.36
Lable 4 (L4)	1	11.36
	5	5.68
	10	11.36
Lable 5 (L5)	1	0.754
	5	3.77
	10	7.54
Total Storage Required (10years)	98.44 MB	

5. Conclusions

The communication between smart meters and home appliances can occur via several communication protocols. These protocols include ZigBee, Ethernet, and Wi-Fi. The data exchanged between the smart meters and utility company travel through several networks. Usually, the data transmitted by intelligent meters go through several data collectors and other smart meters before reaching the utility center. The smart meters connected in the AMI also act as routing nodes for transferring data. Data collectors and utility communication occur via long-distance communication protocols such as 3G, EDGE, or HSPDA. Short-distance communication protocols like ZigBee or Radio Links connect smart meters with data collectors.

In the AMI, every segment has its communication protocol and transport-level security. Due to the highly distributed nature of the AMI system, wireless technologies are expected to be efficient for low-cost implementation. However, exposure to wireless communication mediums will make the system vulnerable to adversary attacks. Unlike the stringent timing restrictions in transmission or distribution, there is leeway for message latency in instances like metering reading or market price information broadcasting. The time range varies from minutes to hours. Consequently, there is significant importance in providing timely service to the end-users; other security features like confidentiality and integrity are prioritized in AMI than the substation automation system to ensure the reliability and secure exchange of critical customer information like account numbers and balances.

Demand response and advanced metering infrastructure are essential to the smart grid implementation scenario. Here we discuss DR's functional layer and how it exchanges information with the user site and utility service provider; it works bi-directionally. Also, discuss authentication classification, which relies on device-to-device, a device to the network, and user-to-appliance. DR terminals provide a framework for the subsequent functional design for technical and software support.

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